

Resolution of chloroform extract (11 g) on silica gel again afforded bergapten (210 mg from benzene eluates) and byankangelicin (315 mg from benzene-ethyl acetate 9 : 1 eluates). Similarly, methanol extract provided a further quantity of byakangelicin (125 mg) from benzene-ethyl acetate (1 : 1) eluates.

The composition of the volatile oil of the fruits :

Volatile oil of the fruits obtained by hydro-distillation (2.2%, v/w) was examined by tlc and glc. Glc carried out over SE-30 (3.5%) exhibited thirty seven peaks and revealed the following percentage composition : α -pinene, 10.99 ; sabinene, 15.27 ; limonene, 10.14 ; *p*-cymene, 4.22 ; 1,8-cineol, 1.00 ; α -terpineol, 5.61 ; bornyl acetate, 29.6. The components were identified by comparison of their retention time with that of the reference standards.

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Sterols from *Anacardium occidentale*

B. DINDA*, J. CHATTERJEE and (Mrs.) J. BANERJEE

Department of Chemistry, Calcutta University Post Graduate Centre, Agartala-799 604

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THE genus *Anacardium* of family *Anacardiaceae* comprises^{1,2} of 15 species mostly found in tropical America from Mexico to Peru, Brazil, South Africa, Madagascar, Mozambique, West Indies and South East Asia, and from Ceylon to Philippines. The species, *Anacardium occidentale* Linn. (local name : *Kaju Badam*) has been introduced in the hotter parts of India like West Bengal, Tripura, Orissa, Madras, Bombay, Goa, Cochin and Travancore. The bark tar of this plant is used³ in the treatment of leprosy and ulcers. The plant yields a pale yellow to reddish gum which exudes in stalactiform masses. This gum has insecticidal properties⁴. Previous investigations⁴⁻¹² on various parts of this plant have revealed the presence of anacardic acid, fatty acids, phenolics, amino acids, proteins, sugars and tannins. As a part of our programme to exploit the medicinal plants of India, we reinvestigated the stem-bark of this plant and could be able to isolate four sterols from the petrol extract. In this note, we report the isolation, characterisation and relative occurrence of these sterols. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first report of sterols from the genus *Anacardium*.

The stem-barks of *A. occidentale* collected from the campus area of this centre in September 1985 were air-dried and milled. The milled stem-bark (1 kg) was extracted with petrol (b.p. 60–80°) in a Soxhlet for 48 h. The petrol extract was distilled to a small volume and the concentrated extract was evaporated to a gummy residue (2.1 g). This residue was column chromatographed over silica gel (60–120 mesh). The benzene eluate on evaporation of solvent gave a solid residue which was homogeneous on tlc. This solid residue on repeated crystallisation from benzene-chloroform mixture afforded shining crystals (0.04 g), m.p. 130°.

The crystalline solid gave positive Salkowski reaction and Liebermann-Burchard test for steroids. The ir spectrum (KBr) of the solid showed $\nu_{\max}$ at 3 420 (OH), 2 940 (CH), 2 880 (CH), 1 640 (C=C), 1 465, 1 385, 1 080 and 980 cm^{-1} . The EI-mass spectrum of the solid was diagnostic to ascertain the skeletal structure. The spectrum showed significant peaks at *m/z* (relative abundance in percent) 414 [M]⁺(84.9), 399 [M -Me]⁺(30.2), 396 [M -H₂O]⁺(51.2), 381 [M -Me-H₂O]⁺(38.4), 329 [M -85]⁺(34.9), 303 [M -C₇H₁₁O]⁺(51.2), 273 [M -SC(side chain)]⁺(37.2), 272 [M -SC-H]⁺(9.4), 271 [M -SC-2H]⁺(9.8), 255 [M -SC-H₂O]⁺(53.5), 253 [M -SC-H₂O-2H]⁺(2.8), 231 [M -SC-C₈H₈]⁺(32.6), 229 [M -SC-C₈H₈]⁺(16.4), 213 [M -SC-C₈H₈-H₂O]⁺(67.4), 211 [M -SC-C₈H₈-H₂O]⁺(2.3), 144(74.4), 10/(57.0), 105(39.5), 55(73.3) 43(100.0), 412[M_1]⁺(14.0), 394 [M_1 -H₂O]⁺(2.3), 379

$[M_1 - Me - H_2O]^+(2.3)$, 369 $[M_1 - C_8H_7]^+(3.5)$, 327 $[M_1 - 85]^+(2.3)$, 314 $[M_1 - 98]^+(4.7)$, 400 $[M_2]^+(20.9)$, 385 $[M_2 - Me]^+(7.0)$, 382 $[M_2 - H_2O]^+(20.9)$, 367 $[M_2 - Me - H_2O]^+(9.4)$, 315 $[M_2 - 85]^+(9.4)$, 289 $[M_2 - C_7H_{11}O]^+(11.7)$, 386 $[M_3]^+(4.7)$, 371 $[M_3 - Me]^+(2.3)$, 368 $[M_3 - H_2O]^+(4.7)$ and 301 $[M_3 - 85]^+(4.7)$ which can be best rationalised¹⁵⁻¹⁶ by assuming the solid to be a mixture of β -sitosterol, stigmasterol, campesterol and cholesterol or their epimers. The relative abundance of the mass peaks also suggested that sitosterol or its epimer be the major component in the mixture. This fact may also be corroborated¹⁶ by its ¹H nmr spectrum in CDCl₃ (100 MHz, TMS as internal standard), which displayed signals at δ 0.66 (3H, s, H-18), 0.76 (3H, d, H-26 or 27 or 28 in case of campesterol), 0.82 (3H, d, H-26 or 27), 0.84 (3H, t, H-29), 0.92 (3H, d, H-21), 0.98 (3H, s, H-19), 3.52 (1H, br s, H-3), 5.01-5.12 (1H, br m, H-22 and 23) and 5.34 (1H, br s, H-6). To find out the approximate composition of the sterol mixture, the solid (0.02 g) was acetylated with acetic anhydride and pyridine and workup of the acetylated product in the usual manner afforded crystals of acetyl derivative (0.012 g), m.p. 118°. This acetyl derivative showed ir absorption (KBr) at ν_{max} 2940 (CH), 2880 (CH), 1745 (C=O), 1650 (C=C), 1510, 1410, 1295 and 1090 cm⁻¹. The EI-mass spectrum of it revealed some significant peaks at m/z (relative abundance in percent) 396 $[M_1 - HOAc]^+(100.0)$, 394 $[M_1 - HOAc]^+(15.3)$, 382 $[M_1 - HOAc]^+(20.9)$, 368 $[M_1 - HOAc]^+(2.3)$, 287 (16.3), 275 (14.0), 255 (54.7), 228 (7.0), 213 (48.7), 147 (61.6), 145 (48.8), 107 (32.6), 105 (34.9), 81 (66.3), 55 (55.8) and 43 (69.7) which may be explained by considering the acetyl derivative as an acetate mixture of sitosterol, stigmasterol, campesterol and cholesterol. The ¹H nmr spectrum (100 MHz) of this acetyl derivative in CDCl₃ (TMS as internal standard) displayed signals at δ 0.67 (3H, s, H-18), 0.78 (3H, d, H-26 or 27 or 28), 0.85 (3H, d, H-26 or 27), 0.87 (3H, t, H-29), 0.94 (3H, d, H-21), 1.01 (3H, s, H-19), 2.01 (3H, s, acetate), 3.60 (1H, m, H-3), 5.01-5.16 (1H, br m, H-22 and 23) and 5.38 (1H, br s, H-6) which are diagnostic of Δ^5 sterols. This acetyl derivative was gas chromatographed on a Pye-Unicam 104 instrument using a glass column packed with 3% OV-17 on 100-120 mesh Gas Chrom Q. The chromatographic conditions were: column temperature, 250°; FID and injection port temperature 280°; carrier gas (N₂) at the flow rate 50 ml/min and chart speed 320 mm/h. The acetyl derivative was found to contain four phytosterols which were identified by comparison RR₁¹⁶⁻¹⁸ with respect to cholesteryl acetate. It was identified as the mixture of the acetates of cholesterol [cholest-5-en-3 β -ol] (R₁, 1.00, 3.0% by peak area); campesterol [(24R)-24-methyl-cholest-5-en-3 β -ol] [1.32, 12.5%], stigmasterol [(24S)-24-ethylcholesta-5, E-22-dien-3 β -ol] (1.46, 15.5%) and β -sitosterol [(24R)-24-ethylcholest-5-en-3 β -ol] (1.64; 69.0%). This relative abundance value may change as the epimers of the said sterols have also same RR₁ values.

The sterols are the metabolites of many secondary metabolism, so the occurrence of these sterols may lead us to find out some compounds which are still eluded to be isolated from the plant.

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Phytochemical Study of *Indigofera mysorensis* Rottl. (N.O. Leguminosae) Leaves

D. ADINARAYANA

S.V.U.P.G. Centre, Kurnool-518 001

and

M. SARADA*

S.P.W. College, Tirupati-517 502

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THE members belonging to the genus *Indigofera* (fam.: *Leguminosae*; sub-fam.: *Papilionoidae*) are widely used in indigenous medicine as anthelmintics, febrifuges and in the treatment of skin

* 6-92, S.V. Nagar, Tirupati-517 502.